

SHORT NOTES

Mercury (II)-Thiourea Complexes

Manzoor Ali and D. V. Ramana Rao

The co-ordination of thiourea to several metals was reported by Rosenheim and Meyer.¹ But several thiourea complexes have been studied in detail only recently.²⁻⁴ Divalent mercury has a $5d^{10}$ configuration and hence can form perfect tetrahedral complexes involving $6s$ $6p^3$ hybrid orbitals for bonding, leaving a perfectly symmetrical nonbonding shell ($d^4\gamma$ $d^6\epsilon$) which causes least perturbation to the preferred stereochemical shape. Several tetrahalo complexes of zinc (II) and mercury (II) have been reported⁵ recently. Oxygen forms weaker covalent links with mercury and requires chelation to provide extra stability, as in case of acetylacetonate complexes, to overcome the weakness of Hg-O bond. Sulphur co-ordination is, however, stronger. The compound, $Hgtu_2Cl_2$ was reported¹ long back. In this communication this compound has been characterised more definitely and two more new complexes are reported.

Dichloro-bis-thiourea-Mercury (II).—Aqueous solutions of mercuric chloride (1.35 g) and thiourea (0.76g) were mixed in 1:2 proportion. A white compound separated immediately. It was filtered, washed, and dried *in vacuo*. It melts with decomposition at 247° . (Found: Hg, 47.1. $Hgtu_2Cl_2$ requires Hg, 47.4%). Halogen could not be directly estimated as $AgCl$ since silver forms a complex with thiourea. The compound is insoluble in water and slightly soluble in ethanol and acetone. The molar conductance (Λ_m) in acetone is 2.2 mhos and hence it is essentially a nonelectrolyte. In solid form, it is diamagnetic ($\chi_g=0$). Hence, it is expected to be a nonelectrolytic, four-co-ordinated, tetrahedral complex of mercury (II) having the formula $[Hg tu_2Cl_2]^0$ involving the use of $6s$ $6p^3$ bonding orbitals.

Dichloro-bis-thiourea- μ -dichloro-Mercury (II).—Ethanol solutions of mercuric chloride (1.35 g.) and thiourea (0.38 g.) were mixed in 1:1 ratio. The white compound was collected, washed with ethanol, and dried *in vacuo*. It does not melt or decompose up to 260° . The compound is diamagnetic in solid form. (Found: Hg, 57.05. $Hg_2tu_2Cl_4$ requires Hg, 57.7%). It is a dimeric chlorine-bridged compound of mercury (II). The compound dissolves in water and subsequently a white solid separates which may be probably $Hgtu_2Cl_2$.

Tetrakis-thiourea-Mercury (II) Chloride.—The compound $[Hg_2tu_4Cl_2]^0$ is soluble readily in excess of aqueous thiourea solution. A freshly prepared sample of dichloro-

1. Rosenheim and Meyer, *Z. Anorg. Chem.*, 1906, 49, 13.
2. Nardelli, Braibanti and Fava, *Gazzetta.*, 1957, 87, 1209.
3. Lopez-Castro and Truter, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 1309.
4. Swaminathan and Irving, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1964, 28, 1201.
5. Dash and Ramana Rao, *J. Ind. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 41, 600.

bis-thiourea mercury(II) (0.5 g.) was treated with a slightly insufficient quantity of aqueous thiourea solution, filtered, and the filtrate was concentrated and crystallised. A white crystalline compound, highly soluble in water, was obtained. It is diamagnetic in solid form and a 1:2 electrolyte in water ($\Lambda_m = 240$ mhos). (Found Hg, 30.2, $[\text{Hg tu}_2] \text{Cl}_2$ requires Hg, 34.8%). The compound is definitely a tetrahedral, ionic complex of mercury (II) even though the compound could not be obtained in a very pure state due to comparative solubilities of the complex and thiourea in water.

The formation of the above three compounds can be schematically represented as follows:

Halogen-bridged, tetrahedral mercury (II) compounds were reported⁶ earlier using phosphorous and arsenic ligands. The above chlorine-bridged complex with sulphur co-ordination is yet another example of the same category of divalent mercury compounds.

DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
REGIONAL ENGINEERING COLLEGE,
ROURKELA-8 (ORISSA).

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6. Evans, E. O., Mann, F. G., Peiser, H. S. and Furdie, D., *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 1209.